

Distribution, Drivers and Management Implications of Riparian Invasive Alien Plant Species in the Ballisodare Catchment

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Statement of Authenticity

I certify that the content of this project is entirely my own work and is submitted in part fulfilment of the B.Sc. (Honours) Degree in Environmental Science with Ecology at the Atlantic Technological University, Sligo.

Any material adopted from other sources is duly cited and referenced and acknowledged as such.

Signed:

Date: 19/04/2026

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Abstract

Invasive alien species (IAS) are an ever-increasing threat to biodiversity and a substantial economic burden, costing Ireland approximately €2.1 billion in 2021. Despite this, repeated failures to manage IAS led the European Commission to refer Ireland to the EU Court of Justice in December 2023 for non-compliance with Regulation (EU) 1143/2014.

Many invasive alien plant species (IAPS) spread across riparian zones as waterbodies act as vectors for propagule dispersal, causing negative ecological consequences. Flooding events are recognised as a major source of riparian IAPS (RIAPS) spread and are becoming more frequent under climate change. However, local information of the spatial extent and distribution of RIAPS is limited. As a member state of the European Union, Ireland is legally obligated under Regulation (EU) 1143/2014 to monitor, manage, and where possible, eradicate IAPS.

This project provides the first dedicated IAPS assessment of the Ballisodare catchment, Co. Sligo through desk analysis and a field study of the Ballisodare and Unshin rivers to map the previous and current IAPS distribution in ArcGIS Pro.

Desk-based analysis found 278 previous records of 14 IAPS and indicated strong associations with urban areas, likely reflecting effort biases. Field mapping 16 km of riparian corridor identified nine RIAPS covering 169,914 m². *Rhododendron ponticum* was spatially dominant (35% of area) followed by *Heracleum mantegazzianum* (20%) while *Reynoutria japonica* only represented 0.7%, despite comprising 66% of desk records. Invaded areas were associated with woodlands and historic estates, with forestry being disproportionately invaded. These findings highlight the need for further RIAPS monitoring and effective upstream management strategies of RIAPS in the Ballisodare catchment.

1. Introduction

Invasive alien species (IAS) are among the leading causes of global biodiversity loss (Kumar Rai and Singh, 2020) and impose substantial global economic costs, estimated to exceed \$423 billion annually (Roy *et al.*, 2023). Despite this, IAS management in Europe has been inconsistent, with Ireland and five other Member States referred to the Court of Justice of the European Union for non-compliance with Regulation (EU) 1143/2014 (European Commission, 2023).

1.1 Background and Conceptual Context

Riparian zones are areas of land which are influenced by and influence adjacent watercourses (NRC 2002). Alien plant species (APS) are species introduced outside of their native range by humans and invasive alien plant species (IAPS) are alien plant species that produce fertile offspring and spread, causing ecological or socio-economic impacts (Richardson *et al.*, 2000).

Approximately 12,000 alien species have been identified in Europe, of which an estimated 11% are invasive (Lucy *et al.*, 2021), marking a serious threat to EU biodiversity. Yet, there is a lack of data regarding the distribution of riparian IAPS (RIAPS) globally (Tian *et al.*, 2026). RIAPS are of particular concern as their spread along river systems can displace native vegetation (Wilson, Freundlich and Martine, 2017), deteriorate water quality (Caffrey, 1999), and impact ecosystem functioning (Vilà *et al.*, 2011).

Locally, the Ballisodare Biodiversity Action Plan (BAP) lists invasive species monitoring and assessment as a potential action, specifically identifying IAPS such as *Reynoutria japonica* (Japanese knotweed) and *Heracleum mantegazzianum* (giant hogweed) to be local issues (Woodrow, 2022). Furthermore, Action 23 of the Sligo BAP 2025-2030 is to ‘Develop an IAS pathway-action plan for the River Unshin SAC and its tributaries’ (Sligo CoCo, 2025).

1.2 Study Area Description

The study area of the project is the Ballisodare catchment, located approximately 8km south of Sligo Town. The catchment spans 645km² and hosts three main rivers: the Owenmore, the Owenbeg, and the Unshin, which converge to form the Ballisodare River. The Unshin River has an associated Unshin River Special Area of Conservation (SAC) (Site code :001898) due to its high-water quality, important floral communities and fauna such as Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*) and otter (*Lutra lutra*) (O’Keeffe and Dromey, 2004; NPWS, 2016). The Unshin River SAC encompasses the riparian areas of the Owenbeg and Unshin Rivers (Figure 1) and therefore may be under threat from RIAPS. In the most recent Water Framework Directive assessments, the Unshin was classed as High ecological status, the Owenbeg as Good, the Owenmore as Moderate, and the Ballisodare as Poor (EPA, 2026). There are also two major lakes in the study area, Lough Arrow, from which the Unshin River flows, and Templehouse Lake which is situated in the middle-lower reaches of the Owenmore River (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The Ballisodare Catchment in Co. Sligo, showing the major river network (Owenbeg, Owenmore, Unshin, and Ballisodare rivers), associated major lakes (Templehouse Lake and Lough Arrow), the Unshin River Special Area of Conservation (SAC), and the area surveyed. Inset map (top right) displays location within Ireland. Figure created in ArcGIS Pro v3.5.0.

Collectively, the Ballisodare catchment contains 12 SACs, two Special Protection Areas (SPAs) and one Natural Heritage Area (NHA) (EPA, 2026), illustrating its ecological value. A map of these areas can be viewed in Figure A1.

This project aims to assess and expand the existing knowledge base of RIAPS within the Ballisodare catchment.

2. Aims and Objectives

The primary aim of this study was to determine the distribution and extent of invasive alien plant species along the riparian zones of the Ballisodare catchment, Co. Sligo.

The objectives of the study were as follows:

- 1) To compile and spatially analyse existing invasive alien plant species (IAPS) records within the Ballisodare catchment.
- 2) To conduct field surveys to locate, record and map riparian invasive alien plant species (RIAPS) along the Unshin and Ballisodare river corridors.
- 3) To quantify the distribution, spatial extent, and cover of RIAPS and evaluate spatial patterns relating to land-use and environmental factors.
- 4) To identify priority areas for management and propose evidence-based control measures for RIAPS.

3. Literature Review

3.1 Ecological Importance of Riparian Zones

Riparian zones are ecotones (transitional zones) between aquatic and terrestrial environments (Gregory *et al.*, 1991). According to Riis *et al.* (2020), over 80% of riparian habitat in the EU has been lost or heavily degraded in the last 200 years. Riparian zones occupy only ~2% of Europe's land area, (~90,000 km²) and are dominated by natural forests (69%) (Clerici *et al.*, 2011). However, this European assessment likely differs from Irish context, as Ireland has very low overall forest cover by European standards (CSO, 2021). National assessments indicate that native riparian woodland is now rare and highly fragmented, and that many waterbodies have very little remaining riparian woodland (Little *et al.*, 2017). Grasslands cover ~56% of Ireland's land area (CSO, 2021), indicating that they likely constitute a high proportion of Irish riparian zones. However, national-scale riparian studies are scarce (Ó Huallacháin *et al.*, 2025).

Despite their small spatial extent, riparian corridors provide disproportionate ecological services. Healthy riparian zones support aquatic food webs and act as wildlife movement corridors (Fischer & Fischenich, 2000), prevent sedimentation, store carbon and provide shading and bank stabilisation, among other ecosystem services (Fu *et al.*, 2016; Anđelković & Radulović, 2022).

Irish riparian zone studies are limited (Ó Huallacháin *et al.*, 2025) however, Ryder *et al.* (2011) verify these functions in an Irish context. Heneghan (2021) argues that Irish riparian zones are an underused nature-based solution for water and climate regulation. Maintaining healthy riparian zones could help Ireland achieve the goals of the Water Framework Directive (WFD) (2000/60/EC) (Boon, Clarke and Copp, 2020), though riparian zones are not explicitly listed as a quality element of the WFD, which is critiqued by Urbanič *et al.* (2022). The ecological sensitivity of riparian zones means they are particularly vulnerable to RIAPS (Tickner *et al.*, 2001).

3.2 Ecological Impacts of IAPS

RIAPS can increase the risk of flooding by indirectly destabilising riverbanks, chiefly during winter dieback (Hardwick *et al.*, 2026), increase hydraulic roughness (Kiss *et al.*, 2019) and otherwise alter hydromorphology (Tickner *et al.*, 2001).

These attributes can cause a variety of ecological consequences, such as a reduction in river water quality. For example, Caffrey (1999) notes that *H. mantegazzianum* can negatively affect *Salmo salar*, by suppressing native vegetation, leading to streambank erosion and increased sediment input. The resulting sedimentation clogs spawning gravel and leads to a reduction of oxygen in developing ova, thereby reducing *Salmo salar* spawning success (Caffrey, 1999; Stubbing, 2009). Furthermore, *H. mantegazzianum* is well known to cause severe burns to the skin via photodermatitis, making it a threat to human health (Klimaszyk *et al.*, 2014). *R. japonica* and *Impatiens glandulifera* (Himalayan balsam) have also been shown to cause similar issues with streambank erosion (Greenwood *et al.*, 2018; Colleran *et al.*, 2020).

RIAPS can severely disrupt native vegetation, leading to reduced flora-fauna interactions and a simplified vegetation structure, thereby providing less adequate habitat for native species (Vilà *et al.*, 2011). *Prunus laurocerasus* (cherry laurel) and *Rhododendron ponticum*, common forest dwelling IAPS have been documented to cause poisoning in domestic animals and out shade forest floors (Dehnen-Schmutz and Williamson, 2006; Cortinovis and Caloni, 2013). Moreover, *R. ponticum* has been proven as an Irish vector of the pathogenic fungi *Phytophthora kernoviae* and *Phytophthora ramorum*, which lead to sudden oak death, among other infections (O' Connor, 2009; Tracy, 2009). The severity of these ecological impacts is closely tied to the traits that enable certain RIAPS to become highly invasive.

3.3 Functional Traits and Invasiveness of Alien Plants

A global meta-analysis by van Kleunen, Weber and Fischer (2010) on IAPS showed significantly higher values of performance related functional traits (e.g. size, growth rate and

resource acquisition) in comparison to alien non-invasive species, indicating that a species' traits are related to its invasive potential.

Ellenberg indicator values attempt to describe the affinities of plant species to certain environmental gradients such as water, pH, nutrient, light and salinity (Hill *et al.*, 1999). Each plant species has unique values indicating their preference to a certain parameter. For example, *Prunus laurocerasus* has a light value of 4, indicating it prefers shaded habitats such as forests (Hill *et al.*, 1999). Ellenberg indicator values provide a useful framework for understanding IAPS' ecological preferences within riparian environments, where disturbance events such as flooding frequently create exposed ground and variable light and nutrient conditions (Richardson *et al.*, 2007).

3.4 Climate Change and its Role in RIAPS Spread

Climate change is driving an increase in flooding rates and intensity (Bergin *et al.*, 2025). Bergin *et al.* (2025) found that two- and 30-day rainfall events are now twice as likely in the south-east of Ireland when compared to pre-industrial times. This is significant as flood events are one of the primary means of RIAPS spread (Anđelković and Radulović, 2022) and heightened flood frequency and intensity is likely to result in increased opportunities for RIAPS spread.

Cushman and Gaffney (2010) highlight that flooding particularly favours clonal RIAPS with buoyant dispersal mechanisms. Moreover, Demian *et al.* (2026) reported a fivefold increase in *Reynoutria* spp. patches in 2022 relative to 2019, following a 100-year flooding event in 2021 that stripped riparian vegetation and transported viable fragments downstream. The findings of Demian *et al.* (2026) are corroborated by Richardson *et al.* (2007) and Richardson and Pyšek (2012) who describe how flood disturbance events create microhabitats and windows of opportunity for IAPS to invade, as competition is temporarily suppressed, and most RIAPS have great capacity to exploit ephemeral resources due to their competitive functional traits

(Cushman and Gaffney, 2010). As invasion pressure increases, so too do the financial burdens associated with control, restoration and lost ecosystem services.

3.5 Economic Impacts of Invasive Species

Beyond their ecological impacts, IAS also incur global economic costs exceeding \$423 billion annually, based on a 2023 assessment by the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (Roy *et al.*, 2023).

Haubrock *et al.* (2021) found a Europe-wide IAS impact cost of €116.2 billion in 2020 from extrapolating data from Invacost v1.0. In the study, Ireland is ranked below average in IAS related costs. However, as the authors note, this may be due to substantial data gaps or underreporting as opposed to low actual impacts.

The first study that attempted to estimate the costs of IAS in Ireland was conducted by Kelly *et al.* (2013) estimating the widely cited annual loss of approximately €261 million to IAS in Ireland. However, the study only accounted for direct market costs, explicitly excluding ecosystem service losses meaning the reported figures are likely a significant underestimate. Later, Jackson (2015) critiques this limitation and argues that the non-use costs are central to estimating the true cost of IAS. By including ecosystem services and incorporating both the use and non-use values, Jackson (2015) estimated annual IAS costs of approximately £650 million, over three times the previous estimate of Kelly *et al.* (2013). There has not been another comprehensive Irish assessment since then. However, Lucy *et al.* (2021) estimated that IAS cost Ireland about €2.1 billion in 2021 by distributing the total EU IAS cost from Haubrock *et al.* (2021) by each country's share of EU gross domestic product. These studies highlight the significant economic burden imposed by IAS on a global, EU-wide and national-scale.

Given the high costs of IAS and the limited funding available to environmental agencies, cost-effective monitoring approaches are increasingly important in monitoring regimes.

3.6 Citizen Science for IAPS Detection and Monitoring

Active citizen science (CS) platforms such as iNaturalist are some of the most cost-efficient methods available in the monitoring of invasive- or other species and are thus a suitable method to addressing the need to monitor trends in global scale biodiversity (Chandler *et al.*, 2017; Howard *et al.*, 2022). CS can aid in monitoring efforts where resources for environmental agencies such as the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) or National Parks Wildlife Service (NPWS) may be limited by funds, time or experts (Donnelly *et al.*, 2013). Involving the public in biodiversity data collection via CS heightens people's connection to conservation and awareness of ecological issues, such as invasive species, as highlighted by Kendall *et al.*, (2021). However, the use of CS data from untrained volunteers has been controversial, particularly when informing decision-making processes (Donnelly *et al.*, 2013). CS data is opportunistic and carries with it inherent sampling and effort biases (Michael *et al.*, 2023).

CS sampling bias is particularly relevant for RIAPS studies, as areas adjacent to urban land are generally more accessible, leading to higher CS engagement (Geldmann *et al.*, 2016). However, urban areas have also been shown to harbour higher IAPS cover than riparian zones surrounded by natural land (Zelnik *et al.*, 2020; Fonseca *et al.*, 2021; Aronson *et al.*, 2017), increasing the likelihood of RIAPS detection in urban adjacent riparian zones.

Additionally, iconic, larger, striking or easily identifiable species are more likely to be recorded than more 'mundane', smaller and cryptic taxa (Callaghan *et al.*, 2021; NBDC, 2024; Kwon *et al.*, 2025). For example, records on the National Biodiversity Data Centre (NBDC) database show there are 8074 records of *Reynoutria japonica* nationwide, whereas *Prunus laurocerasus* has 1935 and *Cornus sericea* (red-osier dogwood), 226 (NBDCa, 2026). This means that despite the relatively large amount of CS data available, invasions of commonly overlooked taxa may not be efficiently detected. Therefore, CS is a useful complimentary monitoring tool but does not replace dedicated RIAPS assessments due its biases and limitations.

3.7 Survey and Detection Methods for RIAPS

A systematic review by Rusnák *et al.* (2022) emphasizes that UAV/UAS (unmanned aerial vehicles/ unmanned aircraft systems) have become one of the most widely used tools for riparian vegetation mapping in the last decade. However, utilising RS technology requires specialists to ensure reliability (Huylbroeck *et al.*, 2020), occasionally leads to misidentification (Belcore *et al.*, 2021) and has high costs associated with data processing (Sun *et al.*, 2021). Additionally, RS is likely to miss understory IAPS or young, emerging plants (Dai *et al.*, 2020; Rusnák *et al.*, 2022).

Thus, field-based surveys remain one of the most reliable approaches for detecting invasive plants, particularly understory or early-stage invasions that may be missed by remote sensing (Dai *et al.*, 2020; Rusnák *et al.*, 2022). Standardised quadrat sampling, transects, and riparian belt surveys are widely used across Europe (Zelnik *et al.*, 2020; Pabst *et al.*, 2022), though methods vary widely which limits comparability between studies. Many riparian IAPS studies rely on greenline transects (transects along riparian vegetation) or quadrat surveys to quantify species abundance, cover and distribution. For example, in the US, Menuz and Kettenring (2013) used a combination of greenline transects and cross-section transects extending 9.5 m from the river channel to record RIAPS presence or absence alongside estimates of cover and a range of environmental variables. Though field-based surveys are more labour intensive and often slower, they can provide robust quantitative data such as stem cover and density which is difficult to capture via remote sensing. Properly assessing RIAPS distribution is important in informing proper management actions and priorities.

3.8 Management and Control of RIAPS

In RIAPS management, an important aspect to consider is the target species' dispersal mechanisms and that rivers may transport propagules downstream (Environmental Agency, 2014). For this reason, management priority should begin at the highest order rivers where IAPS

are present (Kelly *et al.*, 2020). Additionally, small unmanaged or regenerated patches of IAPS can rapidly recolonise treated areas, meaning that inconsistent control efforts are generally ineffective, long-term control and funding are essential to successful RIAPS control (Singh and Byun, 2023).

A global review on the control of IAPS from Weidlich *et al.* (2020) shows that globally, non-chemical methods are the most common approach to IAPS management in ecological restoration being used in approx. 62% of cases studied, with chemical means used in the other 38%. Treatment methods depend heavily on the targeted plant and their dispersal methods as well as the sensitivity of the treatment area. Riparian zones are particularly sensitive as herbicide may infiltrate or runoff into watercourses (Weidlich *et al.*, 2020), making more controlled methods such as stem injection preferable (Spencer, 2014).

For example, according to Caffrey (2001), Nielsen *et al.* (2005) and Uisce Éireann (2019), *H. mantegazzianum* treatment methods involve: manual removal of the roots or cutting/mowing, assuming the appropriate PPE is worn. Alternatively, the most effective chemical treatments involve glyphosate and triclopyr. Regarding *R. japonica*, treatment options include prolonged herbicide treatment (using glyphosate), excavation and disposal (at a licensed landfill facility) or excavation and bunding in situ with herbicide application (NNSS, 2013; Invasives.ie, 2018). Ireland is obliged to manage certain IAS under relevant EU and national legislation.

3.9 Legal and Policy Framework for IAPS in Europe and Ireland

The legal framework for the prevention and management of invasive alien species in the EU is set out in *Regulation (EU) No 1143/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 October 2014 on the prevention and management of the introduction and spread of invasive alien species* (European Union, 2014). This regulation establishes a list of species of EU concern and outlines obligations to all Member States (MS) regarding preventing their spread,

monitoring for early detection, protocols for rapid eradication and management plans for IAPS in each MS territory. Currently, there are 114 total species listed, of which 49 are plants.

Despite being recognised for decades as high-impact invaders in Ireland (NBDC, 2026; Bailey *et al.* 1996), the *Reynoutria* knotweeds (*Reynoutria japonica* and *Reynoutria sachalinensis* (giant knotweed)) were only added to the EU List of Invasive Alien Species of Union concern in 2025 (Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2025/1422). This delay in formal EU listing emphasises the importance of national legislation.

In Ireland, the obligations from Regulation 1143/2014 have recently been transposed via the *European Union (Invasive Alien Species) Regulations 2024 (S.I. No. 374/2024)*. These regulations establish a national list of priority IAS (Table A1), aligned with the EU List of Invasive Alien Species of Union concern (2025) and place clear legal responsibilities on any person who imports, keeps, breeds, transports, sells, or releases a listed species. It is now an offence to sell or knowingly distribute these species. However, the implementation of this regulation has been lacklustre, in fact, the European Commission has taken legal action against Ireland for failing to implement key parts of Regulation 1143/2014, including the requirement to establish and notify effective penalties. Ireland was first warned in 2022 and was formally referred to the EU Court of Justice in December 2023 for these failures. This EU intervention highlights the ongoing lack of IAPS enforcement at a national level.

However, despite being regarded as a high-impact IAPS in Ireland, *Prunus laurocerasus* is a notable outlier in both the EU and national IAS legislation and has been the subject of recent controversy in news outlets (R. Martin *et al.*, 2018; O'Neill and Ó Cochláin, 2025; RTÉ, 2025). *P. laurocerasus* has led to restoration works in local protected areas such as Hazelwood (MKO, 2023), yet it is still sold in garden centres and nurseries (O'Neill and Ó Cochláin, 2025). This represents a gap in legislation listing IAPS of concern in Ireland.

EU and national IAS law has recently been reinforced by the Nature Restoration Law (EU, 2024), which requires all MS to restore degraded ecosystems, including riparian zones. It explicitly identifies the removal or control of IAS as an action for achieving restoration targets in Annex VII (24). Additionally, the WFD provides a legislative framework for the protection and management of waterbodies in the European Union (EU, 2000). The WFD requires all EU MS to achieve 'good ecological status' by 2027. As a pressure on water quality, monitoring and managing RIAPS can contribute towards the objectives of the WFD (Boon, Clarke and Copp, 2020).

4. Methods

4.1 Vegetation Types Included in the Study

This study investigated terrestrial IAPS occurring in the herbaceous and shrub layers of the riparian corridor. Other potentially non-native or invasive, mature canopy-forming tree species such as *Acer pseudoplatanus* (Woodlands of Ireland, 2005) were not included in the scope of this assessment. The invasion dynamics, ecological impacts and management techniques of mature canopy forming vegetation is substantially different from understorey IAPS and would require differing woodland-based methodologies outside the scope of this project (Gioria, O'Flynn and Osborne, 2019; Zhang *et al.*, 2023).

4.2 Study Area Selection

This study was conducted in the Ballisodare (also known as Ballysadare) catchment (WFD code IE35-01), as adapted from the EPA geoportal (EPA, 2026a). Due to the geographic scale of the Ballisodare catchment and the time constraints of this project, field mapping could not be undertaken along each watercourse. Desk based research was performed for the entire catchment area and field surveys were conducted on the Unshin and Ballisodare Rivers (Figure 2). The Unshin and Ballisodare Rivers were chosen as they host significant salmon runs (O'Keeffe and Dromey, 2004; NPWS, 2021) and lie within the Unshin River SAC (site code 001898) which has the following qualifying interests as seen in Table 1 (NPWS, 2019).

Table 1. Qualifying interests of the Unshin River SAC as per NPWS (2021) Conservation Objectives: Unshin River SAC 001898. Version 1. National Parks and Wildlife Service, Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage. Table created in Microsoft Excel.

QI Code	Qualifying Interest	Annex
1106	Atlantic salmon (<i>Salmo salar</i>)	II
1355	Eurasian otter (<i>Lutra lutra</i>)	II, IV
3260	Water courses of plain to montane levels with the <i>Ranunculion fluitantis</i> and <i>Callitriche-Batrachion</i> vegetation	I
6210	Semi-natural dry grasslands and scrubland facies on calcareous substrates (<i>Festuco-Brometalia</i>) (* important orchid sites)	I
6410	Molinia meadows on calcareous, peaty or clayey-silt-laden soils (<i>Molinion caeruleae</i>)	I
91E0	Alluvial forests with <i>Alnus glutinosa</i> and <i>Fraxinus excelsior</i> (Alno-Padion, Alnion incanae, Salicion albae)*	I

Note that 91E0 is a priority habitat as defined under Annex I of the Habitats Directive (92/43/EEC) and threatened by IAPS (Marinsek, 2017). The Unshin and Ballisodare Rivers also interact with other SACs and an SPA. Lough Arrow SAC (001673) and SPA (004050) is the headwater of the Unshin and Union Wood SAC (000638) is adjacent to sections of the river corridors. Downstream, the Ballisodare River discharges into the Ballisodare Bay SAC (000622). The qualifying interests of these sites can be seen in Table A2- in the Appendix. RIAPS have the potential to adversely affect these qualifying interests (Caffrey *et al.*, 2013; Marinsek, 2017; Röschel, 2018).

4.3 Desk Study

4.3.1 Literature Review

A literature review was conducted to identify relevant IAPS, inform survey design and provide ecological and policy background for the study. Literature was primarily identified using the Google Scholar search engine, with additional grey literature sourced from relevant organisations when unavailable via academic databases. Google Scholar was used due to its

broad coverage and ability to capture smaller scale regional studies. The primary search query used was ‘mapping invasive alien plant species in riparian zones’. Boolean operators were used to further filter search results for example to investigate Irish-specific examples, or EU studies. Targeted terms were used for specific topics such as ‘economic impacts of IAS’ and species-specific information.

4.3.2 Compilation of Existing IAPS Records

Existing records of IAPS in the Ballisodare catchment from all available dates (1900- January 2026) were collated from the NBDC’s National Invasive Species Database, the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF), and iNaturalist (NBDC, 2025c; iNaturalist, 2025; GBIF, 2026). The GBIF and NBDC are commonly used sources for Irish IAPS studies (Lucy, Caffrey and Dick, 2021), iNaturalist was included as supplementary information. Data from the Botanical Society of Britain and Ireland (BSBI) was considered; however, BSBI distribution data is primarily available at coarse monad or tetrad resolution. Full-resolution point coordinate data is not downloadable from the BSBI system. As a result, BSBI data was unsuitable for point-based catchment mapping. Nevertheless, some BSBI-originating records may be incorporated into the aggregated datasets available via NBDC or GBIF, depending on the degree of data sharing by vice county recorders.

The data of IAPS from each relevant database in the study area were downloaded and reformatted as usable CSV files (Nekrasova *et al.*, 2021) and subsequently imported into an ArcGIS Pro (version 3.5.0) project (Randall *et al.*, 2022). The collated records were plotted onto a map in their respective locations and categorised by taxon, each with an associated symbology (shape and colour depending on the species and the source of the information).

4.4 Field Surveying

4.4.1 Rationale for Field Surveying

Many modern IAPS assessments utilise UAVs in surveying (Rusnák *et al.*, 2022); this was considered as an alternative method with potential for this study. UAVs are generally quicker, less labour-intensive and easily repeatable. However, they required trained specialists, much greater investment and had associated issues in misidentification or patchiness in surveying (Cook *et al.*, 2025). As Coroi *et al.* (2006) highlight, in person field assessments are often considered more suitable for smaller scale riparian vegetation surveys.

Therefore, field surveys were considered more appropriate for this project and were conducted during appropriate weather conditions (e.g. avoiding floods and high river levels). An ethics form and risk assessment were prepared and approved prior to undertaking field surveying (Tables A5 and A6). Eight field surveys were conducted between December and February, with preliminary scouting trips undertaken in November to investigate access routes and vantage points. GPS accuracy was set to require 10 feet of precision, increased to 15 in areas of low GPS signal, such as Markree Estate.

4.4.2 Field Survey Design

Walking transects were conducted along the riparian zones (greenline transects), scouting for herbaceous and shrub layer IAPS. This is commonplace in other RIAPS surveys as it is the most practical method of botanical surveying in such habitats (Zelnik, Mavrič Klenovšek and Gaberščik, 2020; Pabst *et al.*, 2022). Quadrats were considered impractical as the scale of the survey was too large and specifically focused on IAPS.

Surveys covered the visible and accessible riparian zone with opportunistic continuous surveying along accessible river stretches, as land parcelling was apparent from preliminary

surveying. Where the far side bank was not visible and safe access was available, both sides of the river were surveyed. Where riparian access was infeasible, Visionary Wetland Plus

12×32 binoculars were used to inspect plants across riverbanks or from vantage points. A map of the areas surveyed can be seen below in Figure 2.

In total 16.68 of 29.62 kilometers of the total length of the Unshin and Ballisodare river were surveyed (56%).

Areas with good riverside access such as Ballisodare to Collooney were surveyed in full, other areas were surveyed using a mixture of greenline and vantage points. Unfortunately, due to a combination of land access and time constraints, surveying the entire Unshin was not possible.

4.4.3 In-situ Data Collection

Geographic information systems (GIS) are commonly

used in invasive plant studies with Halmy (2024)

reporting 33% of IAS studies utilising GIS. An Irish

study by Coroi *et al.* (2006) shows that GIS systems can be effectively used to map riparian

vegetation using ArcView (a precursor to ArcGIS Pro). Thus, a combination of Survey123 and

ArcGIS Field Maps was used for in-situ data collection. A Survey123 form was used to

collect data in the field. Surveying location, date and time, the location of IAPS, photos of

IAPS, density measurements and any additional notes were recorded using Survey123.

Density was measured on a 1–5 scale (see Table A3), with 1 representing a single individual

and 5 representing a monodominant stand (one species accounting for most individuals,

>70%). This scale was adapted from other established cover–abundance frameworks

Figure 2. Map showing the greenline transects surveyed for RIAPS along the Ballisodare and Unshin Rivers including urban areas for spatial reference. Figure created in ArcGIS Pro v3.5.0.

commonly used in vegetation surveys such as the Braun-Blanquet and DAFOR indices (Braun-Blanquet, 1964; Massey and Shield, 2016). The scale was intended for semi-quantitative field assessments rather than fine-scale biomass measurements. IAPS identification was aided using guides including the *Invasive Alien Species Pocket Guide* from Sligo County Council (2024) and *Ireland's Regulated Invasive Alien Plant Species* by Torsney *et al.* (2024) to cross-compare sources.

4.4.4 Field Data Processing

The area occupied by each cluster was mapped on site using ArcGIS Field Maps and later refined on desktop using ArcGIS Pro. Each IAPS was colour coded and assigned unique symbology to aid map readability. The resulting map was compared to other spatial GIS data such as urban areas and woodlands to analyse patterns and infer trends.

4.5 Data Analysis

Data analysis was primarily descriptive and spatial. Data summaries were generated highlighting the total area occupied by each species using the mapped IAPS distribution. Hotspots were identified using kernel density, visual clustering and heatmapping in ArcGIS Pro. Desk-based hotspots were mapped using ArcGIS Pro heatmapping (radius= 35) to visually showcase problematic areas, and research was undertaken to investigate the factors leading to such hotspots, including proximity to historic estates, urban areas and habitat type.

5. Results

5.1 Desk-Based Assessment of IAPS records in the Ballisodare catchment

This section summarises the results of the desk-based study of IAPS in the Ballisodare catchment in line with objective 1.

5.1.1 Species Prevalence and Legal Status

278 records of 14 IAPS were found from the desktop study including 184 *R. japonica* (66%), 36 *H. mantegazzianum* (13%), 25 *R. ponticum* (9%) and four *P. laurocerasus* (1.4%). All of which are listed as high-risk invasives by the NBDC (NBDC, 2026b, c, d and e) and some of which are restricted by EU (Regulation (EU) No 1143/2014) and/or Irish legislation (S.I. No. 374/2024) as seen in Table 2.

Table 2. Summary table of the legal status and NBDC risk classifications of all IAPS found from the desk study of the Ballisodare catchment. Where 'Irish Legal Restriction' refers to S.I. No. 374/2024 - European Union (Invasive Alien Species) Regulations 2024 and 'EU Legal Restriction' refers to Regulation (EU) No 1143/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 October 2014 on the prevention and management of the introduction and spread of invasive alien species. NBDC risk categories are as per NBDC invasive risk assessments. IAPS are ordered from most legally restricted to unregulated. Table created in Microsoft Excel.

Invasive alien plant species	Irish Legal Restriction	EU Legal Restriction	NBDC Risk
<i>Reynoutria japonica</i>	✓	✓	High
<i>Heracleum mantegazzianum</i>	✓	✓	High
<i>Reynoutria sachalinensis</i>	✓	✓	Medium
<i>Gunnera tinctoria</i>	✓	✓	High
<i>Rhododendron ponticum</i>	✓	✗	High
<i>Allium triquetrum</i>	✓	✗	Medium
<i>Persicaria wallichii</i>	✓	✗	Medium
<i>Prunus laurocerasus</i>	✗	✗	High
<i>Buddleja davidii</i>	✗	✗	Medium
<i>Clematis vitalba</i>	✗	✗	Medium
<i>Leycesteria formosa</i>	✗	✗	Medium
<i>Symphoricarpos albus</i>	✗	✗	Low
<i>Petasites fragrans</i>	✗	✗	Low
<i>Acaena novae-zelandiae</i>	✗	✗	Not assessed

Both *R. japonica* and *H. mantegazzianum* are legally restricted in the EU and Ireland. *R. ponticum* is regulated in Ireland only, and notably, *P. laurocerasus* is not listed in the EU or Irish legislation despite being classified as a high-risk invasive.

5.1.2 Desk Data Sources

The source of the desk-based data is important to consider as the GBIF and NBDC collate datasets with varying levels of data scrutiny and reliability. An example of the datasets the GBIF results originated from are displayed in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Proportion of GBIF IAPS records by contributing datasets within the Ballisodare catchment (N = 118). Table created in Microsoft Excel.

Most desk-based IAPS data was derived from the Vascular Plant Atlas 2020 (45.7%) and NBDC National Invasive Species Database (NISD) (31.4%) respectively. iNaturalist observations and NBDC Discrete Vascular Plant Surveys represented equal proportions (10.2%). Three records were not attributed to a database.

5.1.3 Spatial Distribution of Desk-based IAPS Records in the Ballisodare Catchment

The spatial distribution of IAPS records across the Ballisodare catchment is shown in Figure 4. These records were compiled from the NBDC, GBIF and research-grade iNaturalist observations. The aim of this map was to provide a spatial summary of previously recorded invasive species records within the catchment prior to field surveying.

Figure 4. Map of past IAPS observations in the Ballisodare catchment from 1900- February 2026. Information sourced from the GBIF, NBDC maps and research-grade iNaturalist observations, searching from 1900-2026. Each IAPS observation is displayed in point form with an associated coloration by species and shape per source (circles for NBDC and GBIF, squares for iNaturalist) with duplicates being removed. ($N=278$). Subfigure (a) shows an inset map of Ballisodare village (Ballisodare River) and subfigure (b) shows an inset map of Collooney (Owenmore River). Figure created in ArcGIS Pro v3.5.0.

The desk-based map appears to under-represent several woodland and shrub IAPS (e.g. *Prunus laurocerasus*) and lacks riparian zone-specific data, with the notable exceptions of the Ballisodare, Collooney and Union wood areas.

5.1.4 Desk-based IAPS Riparian Buffer Analysis

To investigate the riparian zone data available from existing public biodiversity databases, a 30-meter buffer was applied to the river features. This left an area of ~15 meters to each side of the river. Records within the buffer were deemed to be riparian records, displayed in Figure 5.

Figure 5. A map of all desk-based IAPS observations within 30 metres of the river features in the Ballisodare catchment (N=16). Observations obtained from the NBDC, GBIF and iNaturalist, searching from 1900-2026. Figure created in ArcGIS Pro v3.5.0.

Of the 272 desk IAPS records, only 16 (5.76%) were within the riparian zone buffer. Four RIAPS were identified from the desk data, *B. davidii*, *F. japonica*, *H. mantegazzianum*, and *R. ponticum*.

5.1.5 Desk-based Heat Map and Urban Area Analysis

To assess if the IAPS desk records were evenly distributed throughout the Ballisodare catchment, a heat map was made to highlight areas of particularly high IAPS record density (Figure 6). This was overlaid by urban areas to investigate the relationship between IAPS and urban locations.

Figure 6. Heat mapping of desk-based point source IAPS records overlain with CSO urban area data. IAPS records obtained from IAPS observations obtained from the NBDC, GBIF and iNaturalist, searching from 1900-2026. Figure created in ArcGIS Pro v3.5.0.

The spatial distribution of desk records is visibly uneven, with most observations being within or near urban areas. Conversely, the east and west sections of the catchment showed low IAPS record density from the consolidated datasets.

5.1.6 Assessment of Temporal Trends

To consider potential temporal trends, records of IAPS within the Ballisodare catchment were collated from the GBIF, classified into four-year increments, colour coded by time groupings and displayed as points (Figure 7).

Figure 7. IAPS records in the Ballisodare Catchment classified into four-time groups, 2006-2010, 2011-2015, 2016-2020 and 2021-2026 (N=118). Records within the Ballisodare catchment from 1900-2026 were searched on the GBIF. Figure created in ArcGIS Pro v3.5.0.

The temporal map indicates a growth of IAPS records in the catchment, particularly from 2016 onwards. The 2016-2020 data (40%) show a relatively even spatial distribution of records while the 2020-2026 (40%) data is heavily focused around the Ballisodare and Collooney regions.

5.2 Field-based Survey Results

This section presents the results of RIAPS field surveys within the Ballisodare catchment, as per objective 2.

5.2.1 Newly Documented Areas of RIAPS

To showcase newly documented RIAPS, Figure 8 contrasts the desk-based IAPS records with the field data, which is transformed into a line feature for comparison and legibility. The area surveyed is displayed via a red line.

As per Figure 8, there were limited past IAPS observations in the mid-upper section of the Unshin River. Cooperhill and Ardvarney hosted little to no RIAPS observations prior to field assessments.

Figure 8. Map showcasing the segments of the Ballisodare and Unshin Rivers surveyed via a red line and the areas where IAPS were found during field surveys via an orange line. Purple dots show where IAPS have been previously reported in the NBDC, GBIF or iNaturalist databases. Figure created in ArcGIS Pro v3.5.0.

5.2.2 Mapping of RIAPS Field Observations

Field mapping highlighted several clusters of RIAPS (Figure 10 (g)). Maps were prepared to visually showcase the distribution of RIAPS in these clusters as seen in Figure 10. The map panels are ordered from downstream to upstream, starting at the top-left (a) and proceeding rightward in a serpentine pattern. RIAPS polygons use the same colour coding as desk-based mapping for consistency. Images of sites available in Figure A2. Forest data adapted from Perrin et al. (2003) and Perrin and Daly (2010)

(a) Ballisodare River- Ballisodare

(b) Ballisodare River: N4

(c) Unshin River: Ballygrania Bridge

(d) Unshin River: Markree Estate

(e) Unshin River: Cooperhill

(f) Ardvarney

Legend

- Rhododendron ponticum
- Heracleum mantegazzianum
- Cornus sericea
- Prunus laurocerasus
- Symphoricarpos albus
- Clematis vitalba
- Buddleja davidii
- Reynoutria japonica
- Cotoneaster horizontalis
- Rivers
- Forest
- Ballisodare Catchment
- Hotspots

(g) Locator map

Figure 10. Inset maps showing clusters of RIAPS identified during field surveys of the Unshin and Ballisodare Rivers. IAPS polygons are colour-coded as per the legend. Subfigure titles describe the river in the map as well as the name of the area in question. Maps are ordered from downstream to upstream, starting at the top-left (a) and proceeding rightward in a serpentine pattern. The Locator map Figure 10 (g) displays the location of the inset maps relative to the Ballisodare catchment. All maps created using ArcGIS Pro v3.5.0.

The mapped areas varied greatly in both RIAPS composition and spatial coverage. Ballisodare (Figure 10 (a)) represented the most downstream location, accounting for 63% of *H. mantegazzianum* records and all recorded *Reynoutria* spp. Ballygrania Bridge (Figure 10 (c)) supported the highest diversity of RIAPS, with five species recorded, including extensive stands of *H. mantegazzianum* and *R. ponticum*.

Markree and Cooperhill demesnes (Figure 10 (d) and (e)) exhibited woodland invasions dominated by *P. laurocerasus* and *R. ponticum*, with smaller patches of *C. sericea*. Ardvarney (Figure 10 (f)) supported smaller stands of *C. sericea* and *P. laurocerasus*. Unmapped sections of the surveyed riparian zones showed little to no RIAPS presence between these locations.

5.3 Distribution, Extent and Cover of RIAPS

Data summaries of the desk and field results are compiled in this section, including the most recorded species, proportions of land occupied, mechanisms of spread, density and preferred environmental conditions, as per objective 3.

Figure 11 shows the most recorded IAPS in both the field and desk datasets. IAPS are ordered by highest to lowest desk records and colour coded as per species maps. Figure 11 (a) displays the frequency of IAPS records within the Ballisodare catchment sourced from the NBDC, GBIF and iNaturalist. The y axis of Figure 11 (a) is displayed as log 10 as *R. japonica* had many records, skewing the graph. Species with <3 records were grouped into 'all other species' to maintain visual presentation. Figure 11 (b) shows the number of polygons of each IAPS recorded from field surveys of the Unshin and Ballisodare rivers.

Figure 11. Record comparison of IAPS in the Ballisodare catchment across desk-based datasets (GBIF, NBDC and iNaturalist) (a) and field observations along the Unshin and Ballisodare rivers (b). Data labels represent the total number of desk records for (a) and the total number of mapped polygons from field surveying (frequency) for (b). Species are listed in order of number of records from desk data in both (a) and (b) for visual comparison. IAPS are colour coded consistently. IAPS with <3 records were grouped as 'all other species' in subfigure (a). Figure created in Microsoft Excel.

Data from the GBIF, NBDC and iNaturalist (Figure 11 (a)) heavily favoured *R. japonica*, totalling 66.4% of records in the catchment. Field observations (Figure 11 (b)) recorded *H. mantegazzianum* most frequently (36.2%), *R. japonica* was rarely recorded in the field (8.5%), (Figure 11 (a)). 'All other species' in Figure 11 (a) were as follows: *Allium triquetrum* (2),

Clematis vitalba (2), *Reynoutria sachalinensis* (2), *Gunnera tinctoria* (2), *Leycesteria formosa* (2), *Acaena novae-zelandiae* (1), *Persicaria wallichii* (1) and *Symphoricarpos albus* (1).

5.3.1 Field- Based IAPS Area Occupancy and Polygon Summary

The total mapped area, percentage area and frequency of each RIAPS identified in the field surveys of the Unshin and Ballisodare rivers is displayed in Table 3. The area represents the area occupied by a species' mapped polygons in meters squared, the % area describes what % of the area of all RIAPS is occupied by a given species, and frequency indicates how many polygons i.e. how many distinct clusters of a species were mapped. Species are listed from highest to lowest occupied area.

Table 3. Area, % cover and polygon frequency of RIAPS identified during field surveys of the Ballisodare and Unshin Rivers. Area describes the number of meters squared occupied by all polygons of a given IAPS, % Cover shows what % of the total mapped area is occupied by each species, and frequency shows the total number of polygons per each species. Species are listed in order from highest to lowest area coverage. Table created in Microsoft Excel.

RIAPS	Area	% Area	Frequency
<i>Rhododendron</i>	60028	35.33	10
<i>Heracleum mantegazzianum</i>	34092	20.06	38
<i>Cornus sericea</i>	31681	18.65	12
<i>Prunus laurocerasus</i>	24024	14.14	14
<i>Symphoricarpos albus</i>	13222	7.78	10
<i>Clematis vitalba</i>	4222	2.48	2
<i>Buddleja davidii</i>	1194	0.70	8
<i>Reynoutria japonica</i>	1186	0.70	9
<i>Cotoneaster horizontalis</i>	266	0.16	2
Total	169914	100	105

Nine RIAPS were identified and mapped, spanning a total area of 169,914m². *R. ponticum* was spatially dominant, occupying 35.3% of RIAPS area. However, *H. Mantegazzianum* had the highest number of patches (39).

5.3.2 Functional Traits and Environmental Preferences of Field Identified RIAPS

To better understand the ecological niches and environmental preferences of each invasive alien plant species (IAPS) identified during field surveys, Table 4 was prepared. The table lists each species in alphabetical order, describes their means of spread (e.g. vegetative, sexual, or both), functional growth traits (e.g. herbaceous or shrub) and presents the corresponding Ellenberg values as described by Hill *et al.* (1999). The Ellenberg values describe the species' optimal light, water, pH and nutrient conditions

Table 4. Spread mechanisms, functional traits and Ellenberg indicator values of RIAPS identified from field surveying. All Ellenberg indicator values from Hill *et al.*, (1999.) The range of Ellenberg indicators values are displayed in the corresponding column titles (e.g. light value of 1 = highly shade tolerant). Table created in Microsoft Excel.

Latin Name	Spread Mechanism	Functional Trait	Ellenberg Indicator Values			
			Light (1-9)	Moisture (1-12)	Reaction (1-9)	Nitrogen (1-9)
<i>Buddleja davidii</i>	Major seed production, facilitated by wind (Tallent-Halsell & Watt, 2009)	Deciduous shrub	7	5	7	5
<i>Clematis vitalba</i>	Seed dispersal (feathery achenes), vegetative rooting at nodes, self-pollination (Redmond & Stout, 2018)	Woody climber/vine	7	5	7	5
<i>Cornus sericea</i>	Vegetative spread via layering (Kelly, 1990)	Deciduous shrub	6	7	5	6
<i>Cotoneaster horizontalis</i>	Bird-dispersed seeds, rare vegetative spread (Dickoré and Kasperek, 2010)	Deciduous shrub	8	3	8	4
<i>Heracleum mantegazzianum</i>	Major seed production; dispersed by water, wind and contaminated soil (EPPO, 2009)	Herbaceous biennial/perennial	7	6	6	8
<i>Prunus laurocerasus</i>	Primarily spreads via seeds, facilitated by birds; suckering/ layering possible though uncommon (Abrahamczyk, Otto and Weigend, 2024)	Evergreen shrub	4	6	5	6
<i>Reynoutria japonica</i>	Rhizome fragments; sexual seed limited (Woodlands of Ireland, 2005; Tiébré, Saad and Mahy, 2008)	Herbaceous perennial	6	7	6	6
<i>Rhododendron ponticum</i>	Prolific seed, facilitated by wind; vegetative layering and suckering also possible (Harris <i>et al.</i> , 2009)	Evergreen shrub	5	5	3	3
<i>Symphoricarpos albus</i>	Vegetative via rhizomes/suckers; rarely by seed (Stace and Crawley, 2015)	Deciduous shrub	5	6	7	7

5.3.3 Density of RIAPS

The density of each cluster of RIAPS identified during field surveys was assessed on a scale from 1-5 (see Table A3) to add additional context to the mapped polygons and describe the severity of invasion. A summary of each RIAPS' density measurements is seen in Figure 12. The most abundant density class of each RIAPS is labelled with a data callout.

Figure 12. Density class distribution of RIAPS surveyed during field surveying. Density is described from low (D1) to high (D5) (see Table A3) and color-coded in a traffic light system (low= light green, high= dark red). Species are listed in alphabetical order. Figure created in Microsoft Excel.

B. davidii had the lowest overall density as it usually grew in clusters of 1 individual. Conversely, *P. laurocerasus* was the densest on average (59% of records were D5), *R. japonica*, *H. mantegazzianum* and *R. ponticum* also tended to form dense stands. Full data can be seen in Table A4.

5.3.4 Shaded vs Open Habitat Preferences

To investigate the light preferences of the RIAPS mapped in the field, the ratio of IAPS polygons within and outside of forests were compared as displayed in Figure 13.

Figure 13. Comparison of open and shaded habitat occurrence for (IAPS) polygons. Created by calculating number of field mapped RIAPS intersected with forestry using ArcGIS Pro v3.5.0. Figure created in Microsoft Excel.

RIAPS showed clear patterns of open, shaded or facultative growing patterns. Three species were found exclusively in open habitat, two in shaded habitat, and four in both types of habitats.

5.4 Identification of RIAPS Hotspots

As per objective 4, spatial analysis identified several high-priority invasion hotspots, primarily concentrated in the lower catchment, with the most extensive infestations occurring at Ballisodare, Markree, and Collooney. Areas of high RIAPS density are shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14. RIAPS hotspots identified from desk and field-based mapping in ArcGIS Pro v3.5.0. Hotspots (a), (b), (d), (e), (f) and (g) were identified by field surveying and desk analysis. Hotspots (c) and (h) were identified solely from desk analysis and have not been verified in situ.

From the desk and field analyses undertaken, Ballisodare (Figure 14 (a)) contained widespread patches of *H. mantegazzianum* and *R. japonica*. The N4 (Figure 14 (b)) hosted large, continuous stands of *H. mantegazzianum*. Collooney (Figure 14 (c)), similar to Ballisodare, supported both *H. mantegazzianum* and *R. japonica* from desk-based analysis. Ballygrania Bridge (Figure 14 (d)) contained extensive areas of *H. mantegazzianum* and *R. ponticum*. Markree (Figure 14 (e)) supported dense and extensive stands of *R. ponticum*, *P. laurocerasus*, and *C. sericea*, and contained the most upstream riparian occurrences of *H. mantegazzianum* recorded during the study. Cooperhill and Ardvarney (Figure 10 (f) and (g)) contained stands of *P. laurocerasus* and *C. sericea*. Gurteen (Figure 14 (h)) was associated with six desk-based records of *R. japonica*.

6. Discussion

6.1 Desk-based Data – Biases and Spatial Gaps

6.1.1 Species Bias in Citizen Science

Desk-based results were dominated by a small number of species. *R. japonica*, *H. mantegazzianum*, and *R. ponticum* encompassed the majority of observations (88%) (Figure 11). This skew towards certain iconic, well-known invasive species reflects documented biases in citizen science datasets which lead to certain IAS being disproportionately recorded (Callaghan *et al.*, 2021; NBDC, 2024; Kwon *et al.*, 2025).

6.1.2 Desk-based Database Source Analysis

As displayed in Figure 3, there is a mixture of datasets used in the desk-based analysis of this study, some of which have relatively high data reliability, such as the Vascular Plant Atlas 2020 (BSBI, 2020), while others such as iNaturalist have comparatively lower reliability (López-Guillén *et al.*, 2024) and an increased risk of misidentification or incorrect metadata.

6.1.3 Temporal Trends

Temporal trends showed a pronounced increase in database records from 2016 onwards with 80% of the Ballisodare catchment's IAPS records being submitted from 2016-2026 (Figure 7). However, the 2016-2020 and 2020-2026 data show the same total number of IAPS records (n=47), suggesting that the previous growth in records has halted, whether due to actual decreases in effort or possibly targeted treatment eliminating some localised IAPS. Interestingly, the 2016-2020 data is scattered throughout most of the catchment area whereas the 2020-2026 data is heavily focused around the Ballisodare and Collooney regions. However, this spatial clustering likely reflects uneven recording rather than actual invasion patterns.

6.1.4 Under-representation of Riparian Zones

Critically, riparian zones appear to be substantially underrepresented in the available data. As per Figure 5, there were only 16 existing records of RIAPS in the catchment. This represents only 5.76% of total records despite the Ballisodare catchment's extensive riparian network. However, the areas which did have existing RIAPS records (Figure 5) were Collooney and Ballisodare, two urban locations with good riparian zone access. This is consistent with literature which recognizes that easily accessible and urban areas are much more likely to have CS interactions, as is evident from Figure 6 (Geldmann *et al.*, 2016). Although, urban areas are also associated with higher RIAPS populations (Zelnik *et al.*, 2020; Fonseca *et al.*, 2021; Aronson *et al.*, 2017), thus distinguishing differences in effort bias and true invasion patterns is difficult. These findings highlight that the existing IAS data from the NBDC, GBIF and iNaturalist do not reflect true riparian invasion patterns in the Ballisodare catchment and that it is highly likely that many invaded areas are currently unrecorded or under-recorded (Figure 8), which limits effective management opportunities.

6.2 Field-based Assessment of RIAPS' Extent, Composition and Dominance Patterns

Considering the identified bias and limitations apparent in the desk-based study, the field results provide a more representative assessment of up-to-date RIAPS distribution in the Ballisodare catchment.

A total of nine RIAPS were identified from field studies along the Unshin and Ballisodare rivers covering a total invaded area of 169,914 m² (Figure 10). Of these *R. ponticum* covered the most area, followed by *H. mantegazzianum*, *C. sericea*, and *P. laurocerasus* (Table 3). Interestingly, *H. mantegazzianum* had a frequency of 39 which is disproportionately high when compared to *R. ponticum* which had 10 and covered a larger area. This indicates that *H. mantegazzianum* forms small, localised clusters along riparian zones, similar to other light-loving plants *R.*

japonica and *B. davidii* (Table 3, Table 4). The light-loving species have high frequency and low area coverage, likely due to increased competition when compared to the woodland specialist IAPS which comparatively exhibit reduced frequency but increased coverage (John Philip Grime, 1997).

P. laurocerasus, *R. japonica*, *H. mantegazzianum* and *R. ponticum* all showed high density scores (Figure 12) indicating strong competitive ability (Kleunen, Weber and Fischer, 2010) and displacement of native flora, leading to cascading effects on biodiversity (Vilà *et al.*, 2011).

6.3 Species Bias and Ground Truthing

A pronounced species bias was present in the desk-data. As shown in Figure 11 (a) based on desk-data, *R. japonica* was the most recorded IAPS in the catchment (66%), including within riparian zones (19%). Conversely as per Figure 11 (b) it was the sixth most recorded RIAPS in the field, representing only 0.7% of the mapped area. This suggests that *R. japonica* dominates catchment database records rather than actual riparian area, possibly due its legal status, damaging reputation and high rate of recognition (Encarnaço, Teodsio and Morais, 2021; Callaghan *et al.*, 2021; Kwon *et al.*, 2025; Keenan, 2025).

Nationally, the NBDC contains 8,074 *R. japonica* records, whereas *P. laurocerasus* has 1,935 (NBDC, 2026), despite this, *P. laurocerasus* occupied 14% of the total RIAPS area in the Ballisodare catchment whereas *R. japonica* only occupied 1% (Table 3). This reiterates the detection bias and suggests that national datasets may potentially under record lesser recognised IAPS such as *P. laurocerasus* and overrepresent more recognisable IAPS such as *R. japonica*.

6.4 Drivers of Riparian Invasion

Land use was a major factor in the presence and community composition of RIAPS across the catchment's riparian zones.

6.4.1 Historic Estates

A clear correlation was observed between IAPS and longstanding historic estates as seen in Figure 10 (c), (d), (e) and (f) were within the bounds of, or historic near estates which in total represented 66% of field mapping hotspots. Plants such as *P. laurocerasus*, *R. ponticum* and *S. albus* were commonly planted in estates and gardens- in the 1700s, for ornamental purposes and often as cover for game animals such as deer (Dehnen-Schmutz and Williamson, 2006). In this instance, such estates and demesnes appear to remain infested, highlighting that IAPS have not yet been successfully managed in these areas.

6.4.2 Forests

Forests were major hotspots for IAPS (Figure 10), despite comprising only 14% of riparian area (<30m of river feature), forestry contained 45% of IAPS records from field surveying. This uneven distribution is chiefly driven by the dominance of the shade-specialist, acidophilic woodland species *R. ponticum* and *P. laurocerasus* (Hill *et al.*, 1999; Dehnen-Schmutz and Williamson, 2006), which occupied 49% of the mapped invaded area (Table 4).

Ellenberg indicator values (Table 4) and habitat distribution data (Figure 13) reinforce this pattern indicating that *C. sericea*, *P. laurocerasus*, *R. ponticum* and *S. albus* are likely to occupy forests. Conversely, *B. davidii*, *C. vitalba*, *H. mantegazzianum* and *R. japonica* show preference to open habitat and were absent from forestry, with the exception of *H. mantegazzianum* which occasionally tolerated forest edge environments (Figure 13).

6.4.3 Pastures

No RIAPS were found in pastures during field surveys, despite pastures occupying a significant riparian area (~85%). This indicates that riparian pastures may be resistant to invasion within the study area. This is likely due to a combination of management practices such as drainage, cutting and grazing; and abiotic conditions that aren't conducive to certain invasives (Hill *et*

al., 1999). Grazing may have a role in the suppression of herbaceous RIAPS such as *H. mantegazzianum* and *R. japonica* with past studies recognising livestock as a form of control (Beerling, 1991; Dehnen-Schmutz, Perrings and Williamson, 2004; Higgins, 2005; Robinson *et al.*, 2021; Ó Néill and Ó Cochláin, 2025).

Overall, these findings suggest that riparian invasion patterns are strongly influenced by land use with woodlands and historic estates being key RIAPS hubs and pastures showing resistance to invasion.

6.4.4 Species-specific Dispersal Mechanisms and Riverine Spread Potential

From field surveying, *R. ponticum* was spatially dominant, found overhanging the Unshin river in Ballygrania and Markree (Figure 10 (c) and (d)), while *P. laurocerasus* was also found in localised areas, overhanging the Unshin in Markree and Cooperhill (Figure 10 (d) and (e)).

The spread of *R. ponticum* and *P. laurocerasus* is primarily associated with seeds dispersed by wind and birds respectively (Table 4) (Harris *et al.*, 2009; Abrahamczyk, Otto and Weigend, 2024), though their proximity to the river channel increases the likelihood of riverine spread, although, this pathway is seldom documented in the literature.

Other forest-dwelling species such as such as *S. albus* and *C. sericea* (Figure 13) spread primarily via vegetative layering (Table 4) (Kelly, 1990; Stace and Crawley, 2015), thus their spread is much slower, and they are less of an immediate threat.

In contrast to the forest invaders, *H. mantegazzianum* and *R. japonica* are well recognised as disturbance adapted RIAPS. Field surveying found *H. mantegazzianum* to be the second-most spatially dominant RIAPS (Table 3), with *R. japonica* being confined to Ballisodare (Figure 10 (a)), though desk-based research indicates Gurteen and Collooney also host the plant (Figure 4). *H. mantegazzianum* produces high volumes of buoyant seed capable of downstream transport (EPPO, 2009), whereas *R. japonica* has almost no viable seeds in Ireland and spreads

vegetatively via rhizome fragments (Tiébré, Saad and Mahy, 2008) making flood events a key dispersal mechanism. Under climate change scenarios, flooding events are becoming more prevalent (Bergin *et al.*, 2025) and RIAPS with buoyant dispersal mechanisms are projected to benefit disproportionately from the increase in flooding (Cushman and Gaffney, 2010), meaning that *R. japonica* (Demian *et al.*, 2026) and, to a lesser extent, *H. mantegazzianum* are likely to have enhanced dispersal pathways in the near future.

B. davidii, *C. vitalba* and *C. horizontalis* are also ecologically threatening though generally assessed as lower risk in comparison to *H. mantegazzianum* and *R. japonica* (Table 2).

Collectively, these species-specific traits and dispersal mechanisms, alongside the projected increase in flood events suggest that the lower reaches of the catchment are particularly vulnerable to RIAPS colonisation and carry important management implications.

6.5 Potential Ecological and Socio-Environmental Effects of IAPS

The establishment and continued spread of RIAPS within the Ballisodare catchment have several detrimental ecological and socio-environmental effects.

Deciduous RIAPS such as *H. mantegazzianum* and *R. japonica* are likely contributing to localised reductions in river water quality in their concentrated areas (Ballisodare, Collooney, Ballygrania Bridge and the N4). These species outcompete native plants throughout the growing season then die back in the winter, leaving riverbanks exposed and increasing susceptibility to erosion, sedimentation and nutrient runoff (Caffrey, 1999; Stubbing, 2009; Colleran *et al.*, 2020).

Increased sedimentation associated with *H. mantegazzianum* and *R. japonica* can clog spawning gravels used by *Salmo salar*, reducing intragravel flow, oxygen availability to eggs, and overall spawning success (Caffrey, 1999; Colleran *et al.*, 2020). Any potential effects to *Salmo salar* populations could indirectly affect *Lutra lutra* by reducing prey availability (Carss,

Kruuk and Conroy, 1990). As per Table 1, *Salmo salar* and *Lutra lutra* are key conservation objectives of the Unshin River SAC and afforded protection under Annex II and Annex II/IV of The Habitats Directive (92/43/EEC) respectively, as transposed in Ireland by S.I. No. 477/2011.

Additionally, *H. mantegazzianum* is a notable human health hazard, causing photodermatitis from skin exposure to its sap (Klimaszyk *et al.*, 2014). *H. mantegazzianum* has been identified along the riparian areas of Ballisodare (Figure 10 (a)) and Collooney (Figure 4 (b)). The presence of *H. mantegazzianum* in high footfall areas, such as the Ballisodare river walkway represents a considerable public health concern.

Within riparian forests, *R. ponticum* and *P. laurocerasus* are widely cited to outcompete and outshade native flora (Dehnen-Schmutz and Williamson, 2006; Abrahamczyk, Otto and Weigend, 2024). Moreover, *R. ponticum* is a known vector of sudden oak death, among other pathogens (O' Connor, 2009; Tracy, 2009). *R. ponticum* and *P. laurocerasus* are thus a substantial threat to the alluvial forests along the riparian areas of the Unshin River SAC (Table 1) which are protected under Annex I of The Habitats Directive (92/43/EEC).

Together, these impacts showcase that RIAPS pose a threat to the ecological integrity and conservation objectives of the Unshin River SAC.

6.6 Management Implications and Priority Areas

Ballisodare had clear issues with *H. mantegazzianum* and *R. japonica* (Figure 10 (a)), two legally restricted species under both EU (Regulation (EU) No 1143/2014) and Irish legislation (S.I. No. 374/2024). However, it is recommended to treat upstream locations first to prevent recolonisation (Kelly *et al.*, 2020). Markree Estate (Figure 10 (d)) and Ballygrania Bridge (Figure 4) held the highest riparian instances of *H. mantegazzianum* and *R. japonica*

respectively, making them a management priority to prevent downstream spread (Environmental Agency, 2014; Kelly *et al.*, 2020).

The presence of *H. mantegazzianum* and *R. japonica* does not, in itself, mandate eradication or active management. However, legislation prohibits their spread and riparian corridors represent significant dispersal pathways, as outlined in section 6.4.4. Thus *H. mantegazzianum* and *R. japonica* are recommended for management in Markree Estate and Ballygrania due to their spread mechanisms (Table 4), legal status (Table 2) potential to adversely affect the conservation objectives of the Unshin SAC (Table 1), and *H. mantegazzianum*'s potential health risks (Klimaszyk *et al.*, 2014).

Furthermore, woodlands and historic estates within the Ballisodare catchment were shown to harbour shade tolerant and acidic leaning species (Figure 13) such as *R. ponticum*, *C. laurocerasus* and *C. sericea*. *R. ponticum* is listed under (S.I. No. 374/2024) and alongside *P. laurocerasus*, is recommended for management due to their potential adverse impacts towards the Annex I alluvial forests (QI: 91E0) along the riparian areas of the Unshin River SAC.

6.7 Study Limitations

The field study portion of this project was subject to a variety of limitations, chiefly related to the surveying period. A full list of limitations is available in Table 5. For each limitation, a brief description, the potential impact on the results, and where applicable the mitigation measures employed or additional context is provided.

Table 5. A summary of the key methodological limitations identified during the study and their potential impacts on survey outcomes, with corresponding context and mitigation measures. Table created in Microsoft Excel.

Limitation	Description	Potential Impact on Results	Mitigation / Context
Seasonal Timing	Surveys conducted during the Winter months, from November- February	Reduced detectability of herbaceous IAPS. Difficulty distinguishing similar taxa without flowers, leaves or seed structures. Some IAPS unidentifiable or very inconspicuous.	Supplemented with desk-based historic records; identification supported by field guides and photos.
Species Identification	Morphological similarity between taxa (e.g. hogweed spp. vs. <i>Angelica</i> spp.) during non-vegetative periods.	Risk of misidentification or conservative under-recording.	Use of hand lens, photographic verification, and identification cross checked across several sources.
Hydrological Conditions	High river flow during much of the survey period.	Obscured riparian zones. Limited visibility of submerged plants.	Surveys conducted in suitable hydrological conditions where possible.
Land Access Constraints	Large portions of riparian corridor on private (largely agricultural) land. Waterlogged or densely vegetated areas also inaccessible.	Uneven spatial coverage. Potential underrepresentation of IAPS in inaccessible parcels.	Surveyed safe, publicly accessible riparian areas. Vantage points used where applicable.
Spatial Scope	Only the Unshin and Ballisodare Rivers were surveyed in-field. Tributaries excluded.	Catchment-wide conclusions limited. Tributary invasions may be undocumented.	Desk-based records assessed for full catchment overview.
Surveying Methodology	Opportunistic continuous transects rather than systematic sampling.	Semi-quantitative data	Appropriate for large-scale spatial mapping and timeframe of the project.
Temporal Inconsistency	Ballisodare Fishing Club walkway surveyed in May. Remainder surveyed in winter.	Seasonal bias in detection rates.	Acknowledged during interpretation of density and hotspot analysis.
GPS accuracy	GPS inaccuracies may have affected polygon placements	Incorrect shifting of polygons in areas with poor mobile reception.	Where identified attempted to be fixed on desktop. Markree forest was a particular difficulty in this regard.

While these limitations highlight some constraints regarding detection and spatial coverage, they do not undermine the results of the study and are acknowledged in full. It is recognised that the winter survey period is not optimal for RIAPS surveying and that subsequent surveys in the summer could reveal new RIAPS occurrences within the catchment.

7. Conclusions and Recommendations

7.1 Conclusion

This study represents the first effort of a catchment-scale assessment of riparian invasive alien plant species (RIAPS) in the Ballisodare catchment. A total of 278 past records of 14 IAPS were identified from desk research, while field surveys along 16.68 km of the Unshin and Ballisodare rivers recorded nine RIAPS occupying an area of 169,914 m².

Invasion patterns were uneven with just four species comprising 88% of total area, most notably *Rhododendron ponticum* (35%) and *Heracleum mantegazzianum* (20%). Land use arose as an important factor, with historic estates and riparian woodland acting as invasion hotspots, while pasture showed resilience to invasion.

A clear discrepancy was found between desk-based datasets and field observations. *R. japonica* was significantly overrepresented in the desk-based data (66% of records) yet only accounted for 0.7% of the identified RIAPS area during field surveys. Additionally, riparian invasion information was limited, comprising only 5.7% of total desk records. This suggests that existing datasets do not accurately capture catchment-wide invasion patterns, particularly in riparian zones.

The distribution and extent of RIAPS identified in this study indicate a substantial pressure towards the conservation objectives of the Unshin River SAC. Targeted control of *H. mantegazzianum* in Markree and *R. japonica* in Ballygrania could reduce the risk of downstream spread and further establishment. Management of *R. ponticum* and *P. laurocerasus* is recommended to prevent damage to the alluvial forests of the Unshin River SAC.

7.2 Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed.

7.2.1 Management

- Prioritise upstream infestations of high-risk species *H. mantegazzianum* and *R. japonica* in Markree and Ballygrania to limit downstream dispersal via riverine pathways. Additionally, begin upstream management of *R. ponticum* and *P. laurocerasus* within riparian woodlands.
- All management efforts should be followed by long-term monitoring and coordinated at a catchment scale to account for the hydrological connectivity of riparian zones.
- With the first RIAPS survey effort of the Unshin and Ballisodare rivers now completed, develop an evidence-based IAS pathway action plan for the Unshin River SAC and its tributaries to support management efforts, in line with action 23 of the Sligo Biodiversity Action plan (SligoCoCo, 2025).
- Given its high density, competitive ability and potential for impact on riparian woodland, future inclusion of *P. laurocerasus* to S.I. No. 374/2024 should be considered.

7.2.2 Monitoring

- Prioritise riparian-specific field surveys particularly in rural and upstream areas of the Ballisodare catchment to address the underrepresentation of riparian records (5.76%) identified in this study
- Undertake seasonally appropriate surveys targeting herbaceous species in the summer and evergreen species in the winter.
- Expand field surveys to unassessed waterbodies within the catchment, including the Owenbeg, Owenmore, Templehouse Lake, Lough Arrow and associated tributaries to

identify potential unassessed invasion pathways, which were identified as a limitation of this study. Where possible, seek access to previously unsurveyed riparian corridors.

7.2.3 Community Engagement & Citizen Science

- Given the taxonomic bias present in citizen science datasets (section 6.1.), increase local knowledge of invasive plants through targeted identification and reporting workshops (Woodrow, 2022).
- Given its prevalence, install *H. mantegazzianum* signage in Ballisodare and Collooney to better inform the public of the health and safety risks associated with *H. mantegazzianum*'s phototoxic sap (Rzymiski *et al.*, 2014), as per action 7 of the Ballisodare BAP (Woodrow, 2022).

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8. Appendix

Figure A1. Protected areas within and surrounding the Ballisodare Catchment including Special Areas of Conservation (SAC), Special Protection Areas (SPA), and Natural Heritage Areas (NHA). Numbers displayed on the map correspond to the protected area key listed below.

No.	Protected Area (Designation)	Site Code
1	Lough Arrow (SPA)	004050
2	Ballysadare Bay (SPA)	004129
3	Ballysadare Bay (SAC)	000622
4	Bricklieve Mountains and Keishcorran (SAC)	001656
5	Cloonakillina Lough (SAC)	001899
6	Dooastle Turlough (SAC)	000492
7	Flughany Bog (SAC)	000497
8	Knockalongy and Knockachree Cliffs (SAC)	001669
9	Lough Arrow (SAC)	001673
10	Ox Mountains Bogs (SAC)	002006
11	Templehouse and Cloonacleigha Loughs (SAC)	000636
12	Turloughmore (SAC)	000637
13	Union Wood (SAC)	000638
14	Unshin River (SAC)	001898
15	Slieveward Bog (NHA)	001902

Table A1. IAPS lister under the European Union (Invasive Alien Species) Regulations 2024 (S.I. No. 374/2024). Species identified during field surveys highlighted in bold.

Common name	Scientific name	Common name	Scientific name	Common name	Scientific name	Common name	Scientific name
American skunk-cabbage	<i>Lysichiton americanus</i>	Hottentot-fig	<i>Carpobrotus edulis</i>	Giant knotweed	<i>Reynoutria sachalinensis</i>	Water chestnut	<i>Trapa natans</i>
A red alga	<i>Grateloupia doryphora</i>	Japanese knotweed	<i>Reynoutria japonica</i>	Giant-rhubarb	<i>Gunnera tinctoria</i>	Water fern	<i>Azolla filiculoides</i>
Brazilian giant-rhubarb	<i>Gunnera manicata</i>	Large-flowered waterweed	<i>Egeria densa</i>	Giant salvinia	<i>Salvinia molesta</i>	Water-primrose	<i>Ludwigia</i> (all species)
Broad-leaved rush	<i>Juncus planifolius</i>	Mile-a-minute weed	<i>Polygonum perfoliatum</i>	Himalayan balsam	<i>Impatiens glandulifera</i>	Waterweeds	<i>Elodea</i> (all species except <i>Elodea Canadensis</i>)
Cape pondweed	<i>Aponogeton distachyos</i>	New Zealand pigmyweed	<i>Crassula helmsii</i>	Himalayan knotweed	<i>Koenigia polystachya</i>	Wireweed	<i>Sargassum muticum</i>
Cord-grasses	<i>Spartina</i> (all species and hybrids)	Parrot 's feather	<i>Myriophyllum aquaticum</i>	Fringed waterlily	<i>Nymphoides peltata</i>	Three-cornered leek	<i>Allium triquetrum</i>
Curly waterweed	<i>Lagarosiphon major</i>	Rhododendron	<i>Rhododendron ponticum</i>	Giant hogweed	<i>Heracleum mantegazzianum</i>	Wakame	<i>Undaria pinnatifida</i>
Dwarf eelgrass	<i>Zostera japonica</i>	Salmonberry	<i>Rubus spectabilis</i>	Floating pennywort	<i>Hydrocotyle ranunculoides</i>	Spanish bluebell	<i>Hyacinthoides hispanica</i>
Fanwort	<i>Cabomba caroliniana</i>	Sea-buckthorn	<i>Hippophae rhamnoides</i>				

Table A2. Qualifying interests of SAC and SPA's associated with the Unshin and Ballisodare Rivers. Sourced as per relevant NPWS conservation objectives series.

Site Name / Code	Qualifying Interests
Lough Arrow SAC (001673)	• Hard oligo-mesotrophic waters with benthic vegetation of <i>Chara</i> spp. • Otter (<i>Lutra lutra</i>)
Lough Arrow SPA (004050)	• Little Grebe (<i>Tachybaptus ruficollis</i>) • Tufted Duck (<i>Aythya fuligula</i>) • Wetlands and waterbirds
Union Wood SAC (000638)	• Old sessile oak woods with <i>Ilex</i> and <i>Blechnum</i> in the British Isles
Ballysadare Bay SAC (000622)	• Estuaries • Mudflats and sandflats not covered by seawater at low tide • Embryonic shifting dunes • Shifting dunes along shoreline with <i>Ammophila arenaria</i> • Fixed coastal dunes with herbaceous vegetation • Humid dune slacks • Narrow-mouthed Whorl Snail (<i>Vertigo angustior</i>) • Harbour Seal (<i>Phoca vitulina</i>)

Table A3. Density scoring system for field surveying of IAPS. Scoring system adapted from commonly used vegetation abundance and dominance assessment frameworks such as the Braun-Blanquet and DAFOR scales (Braun-Blanquet, 1964; Massey and Shield, 2016).

Score	Description	Approximate % cover
1	Single individual or very sparse	<1%
2	Scattered individuals or small patch	1-10%
3	Frequent individuals forming patches	10-30%
4	Dense stand	30-70%
5	Monodominant or near monodominant	>70%

Figure A2. Photos of RIAPS identified in field surveying hotspots along the Unshin and Ballisodare Rivers. Inset maps created in ArcGIS Pro v.3.5.0, figure created in Microsoft PowerPoint.

Table A4. Meters squared occupied by each density class of each RIAPS identified from field surveying along the Unshin and Ballisodare Rivers. Results are colour coded from high (red) to low (green) or zero (grey).

RIAPS		M ² Occupied by each Density Class				
Common name	Scientific name	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5
Butterfly bush	<i>Buddleja davidii</i>	712	0	73	0	0
Travellers Joy	<i>Clematis vitalba</i>	0	421	4222	0	0
Red Osier Dogwood	<i>Cornus sericea</i>	0	3214	20225	4570	51
Cotoneaster	<i>Cotoneaster spp.</i>	0	30	71	0	0
Giant Hogweed	<i>Heracleum mantegazzianum</i>	0	105	10969	14378	1784
Cherry Laurel	<i>Prunus laurocerasus</i>	0	142	3905	6113	14817
Japanese Knotweed	<i>Reynoutria japonica</i>	0	0	42	264	85
Rhododendron	<i>Rhododendron ponticum</i>	0	0	1916	830	631
Snowberry	<i>Symphoricarpos albus</i>	1659	1859	2116	7587	0

Table A5. Project risk assessment form submitted to ATU ethics committee.

Student Name	Conall Bonner
Student Number	S00236449
Title of Course	Environmental Science with Ecology
Year of Course	4 th
Start Date of Project	29/9/2025
Supervisors Name	Lisa Cronin
<p>This project aims to investigate the types and abundance of invasive plant species along the riparian zones of the Ballisodare River catchment (the Unshin, Owenmore, Owenbeg and Ballisodare River). This will involve a combination of fieldwork along the rivers and deskwork, a lot which will include GIS mapping to prepare a map of the location of the invasive species.</p> <p>No chemicals shall be necessary, and equipment will be quite limited e.g. a clipboard to take notes, phone for communication and photography, GPS to mark the location of invasives, a buoyancy aid for riverside work and possibly a drone to have aerial photos and visual access to places which may be difficult to traverse on foot e.g. dense vegetation across the river. (The drone will be provided by Ballisodare Fishing Club)</p> <p>Two other students are to be working along the same river catchment, and we intend to accompany one another to avoid any lone working.</p>	

Project Risk Assessment

Prior to starting, the Project Supervisor and Student must identify the hazards which maybe present and state what control measures they will be put in place to control the Risk. Below is a **non-exhaustive list** of the potential Hazards which **may be** present, these can be used as a starting point, delete those which do not apply. Ensure you identify the controls needed. These can include using a less dangerous chemical, training on use of equipment, good lab or workshops practices, reporting defects, first aider present, following the out of hours access and off campus activities procedures and other procedures, use of PPE etc)

Potential Hazards	Controls Required
Slips, trips and falls	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wear suitable footwear • Avoid uneven terrain where possible.
Drowning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wear a lifejacket near waterbodies • Avoid entry to rivers • Avoid adverse weather conditions
Lone working	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Work alongside a colleague • Carry a charged mobile phone with signal • Inform someone of estimated departure & return time
Waterborne pathogens	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cover cuts • Get injections (e.g. tetanus shot) • Wash hands regularly
Wildlife	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wear long clothing • Avoid disturbance
Invasive species	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Avoid the spread of invasives • Avoid contact with potential skin irritants (e.g. Giant Hogweed)
Vehicle/roadside access	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Park safely • Wear hi-vis clothing
Members of the public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engage respectfully, explain work being undertaken • Avoid arguments
Crossing fences or walls	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use designated access points • Avoid climbing over obstacles
Livestock	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Avoid entering/passing through areas occupied by livestock (e.g. bulls, cows)
Trespassing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure land is either public or that landowner's consent has been obtained
Drone operation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Colliding with overhead wires • Potential to disrupt wildlife
Exposure to the elements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wear appropriate clothing • Check the forecast in advance • Avoid fieldwork during adverse weather

Category of Supervision Required

Category	Level of Risk Present	Tick one
Category A	The risks associated with the work and/or the inexperience of the worker are such that the work must be supervised directly by a competent person (the supervisor or his/her authorized nominee), at least until the supervisor is satisfied that the student can follow correctly the appropriate scheme of work. Note: this might apply only to a small section of the whole project.	<input type="checkbox"/>
Category B	The risks associated with the work and/or the inexperience of the worker is such that the work may	<input type="checkbox"/>

Potential Hazards		Controls Required
	not be started without the supervisor's or his/her authorized nominee's advice and approval.	✓
Category C	The Risks are such that the work requires considerable care, but it is considered that the worker is adequately trained and competent in the procedures involved.	<input type="checkbox"/>
Category D	The risks are low and carry no special supervision requirements.	<input type="checkbox"/>
Risk Assessment Sign Off		
Student Sign and Date	8/10/2025	
Supervisor Sign and Date	Lisa Cronin 10/10/2025	

Table A6. Submitted project ethics approval form

This project aims to investigate the types and abundance of invasive plant species along the riparian zones of the Ballisodare River catchment (the Unshin, Owenmore, Owenbeg and Ballisodare River). This will involve a combination of fieldwork along the rivers observing and identifying ant invasive plant species and the area they occupy (gathering co-ordinates) and deskwork, a lot which will include GIS mapping to prepare a map of the location of the invasive species as well as calculating how prominent each are and estimating the cost to treat them so that future works have a starting point when reaching contractors.

No chemicals shall be necessary, and equipment will be quite limited e.g. a clipboard to take notes, phone for communication and photography, GPS to mark locations of invasives, a buoyancy aid for riverside work and possibly a drone to have aerial photos and visual access to places which may be difficult to traverse on foot e.g. dense vegetation across the river. (The drone will be provided by Ballisodare Fishing Club). Two other students are to be working along the same river catchment, and we intend to accompany one another to avoid any lone working.

Project Aims:

- To create a GIS map showing the distribution and extent of invasive plant species in the Ballisodare catchment.
 - Estimate the area affected by each invasive species
 - Calculate an estimate of treatment costs
 - Develop mitigation/ management recommendations
- Assess the potential ecological impacts of invasive plant species on native riparian vegetation and ecosystem functions

Project Objectives:

- Select catchment area and map riparian zones using GIS or satellite imagery

Table A6. Project Ethics Form

	Yes	No	N/A	If you answer yes, please provide additional information.
Does your research involve children or young people aged under 18 years?		✓		
Will you have access to documents containing sensitive personal data about individuals? If yes,		✓		

will consent be obtained?				
Does your research involve prisoners or others in custodial care (e.g. young offenders)?		✓		
Does your research involve individuals with learning or communication difficulties?		✓		
Does your research involve those engaged in suspected illegal activities (e.g. drug taking; crime, illegal internet behaviour)?		✓		
Does your research involve vulnerable service users (e.g. patients, homeless)?		✓		

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	Yes	No	N/A	If you answer yes please provide additional information.
Does your research involve animals?		✓		
Does your research raise any issues of risk for you? (Especially if taking place outside working hours or off Institute premises)	✓			There are risks involved including: Slips, trips and falls, working near waterbodies (rivers), waterborne pathogens etc. A buddy system will be put in place to avoid lone working. Suitable safety measures will be put in place as per the risk assessment form.
To the best of your knowledge Is there potential for physical		✓		

and/or psychological harm/distress to participants?				
Will informed consent/assent be obtained from the participants?			✓	
Will you advise participants what you will do with the results of the study and who will have access to this information?			✓	
Will you advise participants that they may withdraw from the research at any time and for any reasons?			✓	

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	Yes	No	N/A	If you answer yes please provide additional information.
Will financial/in-kind payments (other than reasonable expenses and compensation for time) be offered to participants? (Indicate how much and on what basis this has been decided)		✓		
Does your project engage with a vulnerable group, other than those listed above?		✓		
Does your research involve biological fluids/tissue/biopsies?		✓		

How will potential participants in your project be:

	Please provide a brief explanation
(i) Identified	N/A
(ii) approached	N/A
(iii) recruited	N/A

What measures will be put in place to ensure the confidentiality of personal data?	N/A
--	-----

What measures will be put in place to ensure the safe storage of all collected data?	N/A
--	-----

If there are any other potential ethical issues that you think that the Committee should consider, please explain them on a separate sheet. It is your responsibility to bring to the attention of the Committee any ethical issues not covered on this form.

Please attach a project proposal (where available), proposed participant information sheet and consent forms to this application.

Student(s) Signature

Where appointed, Supervisor Signature Date

Lisa Cronin 10/10/2025